

MOISTURE SORPTION IN ARAMID COMPOSITE ON DIFFERENT STRUCTURAL AND PHYSICAL LEVELS

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ABSTRACT

Moisture sorption in an aramid-epoxy composite and its structural components — an aramid fibre and an epoxy matrix was studied theoretically and experimentally by sorption and different physical methods. The Fick law for anisotropic materials was used to describe sorption experiments. A method for accelerated determining of moisture sorption characteristics in anisotropic fibre-reinforced composite has been proposed. Calculation of the sorption characteristics of a material on structural levels: fibre + matrix, one-dimensional monolayer composite, multilayer composite was made. Moisture transport process in a thin parallel-plane multilayer plate with different materials of layers has been also considered using a mathematical model and a program for numerical calculation.

It was experimentally shown that the moisture sorbed by the aramide composite (really by all it's components on different structural levels) significantly alter its physical and mechanical characteristics [1, 2]. This make it important to study the moisture absorption in the material. For a rigorous use of a some moisture sorption process model it is necessary to investigate the absorption mechanism, the water molecules distribution in the material and the total reversibility of the moisture absorption process.

The experiments were carried out on the moistened samples of unidirectional aramide composite, prepared from epoxy binder EDT-10 and aramide fiber SVM with reinforcement factor of 0.6 by volume, or its component. The samples for physical experiments were moistened in desiccators over saturated salt solutions, that provide atmosphere 47, 78 and 98 % RH.

The reversibility of moisture sorption process in aramide composite was investigated by the thermogravimetric (TG) method using thermal analysis system Mettler, Switzerland.

Fig. 1. Kinetics of weight loss by samples of aramide composite with a moisture content of 7.9 (1), 5.7 (2), 2.8 (3), 0.7% (4) and yield of low-molecular-weight products (5).

The thermal analyzer had a module for TG analysis of samples weighing from 5 to 30 mg with error of weighing of $0.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mg in an atmosphere of an inert gas. The experimental curves of the weight loss during the TG studies (Fig. 1) contain information on desorption of moisture and departure of low-molecular-weight fractions from the samples (with relative weight moisture content from 0.7 to 7.9%), including possible products of thermal decomposition. The kinetics of the departure of low-molecular-weight products (curve 5 in Fig. 1) was obtained using the weight loss isotherms for different temperature levels plotted from the data Fig. 1. The successive subtraction of curve 5 from curves 1-4 made it possible to determine the kinetics of desorption of moisture for samples with a different moisture content. The total amount of moisture separated from the material during desorption did not differ from the mass concentration of moisture determined during sorption by more than $\pm 5-10\%$.

On this basis, it is possible to assume that moisture absorption in the aramide composite is a reversible process up to a level of 8wt.% [3].

The degree of dispersion of the moisture sorbed by the composite was studied using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) of samples weighing 10-15 mg. To prevent condensation of moisture and formation of frost on the sample and walls of the measuring cell during cooling, the cell was blown through with nitrogen at a rate of $60 \text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$. A comparison of the DSC diagrams (Fig. 2), characterizing absorption of heat by the samples of composite with moisture content of 0.5 to 7.9 wt.% shows that no marked absorption of energy due to melting of the crystallized part of the water is observed in the region of negative temperatures. It is possible to assume that there are no associates of water of significant size capable of crystallization in the tested composite containing up to 8 wt.% water.

Fig. 2. DSC diagrams of samples of aramide composite with a moisture content of 7.9 (1), 5.7 (2), 2.8 (3), 0.7% (4).

Fig. 3. NMR spectra of composite with moisture contents of 8.0 (1), 15 % (2); free water (3).

The mobility and interaction of sorbed water molecules with the macromolecules of the components of composite was studied by the high-resolution ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance method (NMR) [4]. The high-resolution NMR spectra were taken at 22 °C on spectrometer with a proton resonance frequency of 60 MHz. The sensitivity of the spectrometer allows one to determine the presence of water in the free state at a concentration of 0.1 % and higher. NMR spectra are presented in Fig. 3 (moisture content 15.7 % had samples, moistened in water). Experiment results have shown that the lines of water cannot be recorded in the composite samples containing 0, 1.9, and 5.1 wt.% water. Evidently, at such concentrations the main part

of the water molecules is strongly bound to the macromolecules of the composite components and gives a broad line in the NMR spectrum which combines with the background. At a moisture content of 8.0 % a relatively intensive broadened line is observed. The increase in the intensity of the line when the moisture content of the samples increased from 8.0 to 15.7 % is caused by an increase in the concentration of weakly bound water in the composite, while its narrowing is related to an increase in the mobility of a part of the sorbed molecules.

It can be supposed that the average binding force between the water molecules and the macromolecules of the composite components weakens as its content in the composite increases. Apparently, when moisture is absorbed in the composite, it is sorbed in several layers. Most strongly bound to the macromolecules are the water molecules of the first layer, which is formed already at low concentrations. Water in such layers gives a broad spectra line not fixed by the high-resolution NMR. An increase in the moisture concentration leads to the completion of the following sorption layers; the mobility of the water molecules in these layers is noticeably higher and they are characterized by a narrower line of the NMR signal. Experimental data indicates that no free water is present in the investigated unidirectional composite. The moisture sorbed by the material does not form macroscopic associates. The data obtained by physical methods suggests the diffusion mechanism of moisture sorption by material.

Moisture sorption kinetics was studied on samples of the composite, the epoxy binder and the microplastic MP (SVM thread soaked in the epoxy binder and than cured). The last one had reinforcement factor of 0.95 by volume and further was taken as a reinforcement filler. Moisture and temperature conditions of the sorption experiments which were executed in climatic camera, Mack-Been scales for MP, and in desiccators are given in Table 1. Typical moisture sorption curves are shown in Fig. 4. From this figure can be noticed that the sorption process satisfies external Fick model conditions: the presence of an initial linear segment of the sorption curve in the moisture content—square root of time coordinate axes, the absence of a visible two-stage sorption process, the asymptotic approach to the equilibrium state with an unrestricted increase

Table 1. Moisture and temperature conditions of the sorption experiments

T, °C	φ, %										
	16	20	24	40	47	50	60	78	80	98	100
5									bc		
20		b	m		<u>bc</u>	b		<u>bcm</u>		<u>bcm</u>	
29									bc		
45									bc		
60	b			bc			bc		bc		bc

b — binder, c — composite, m — microplastic, — experiment in desiccators.

in the sorption time. Therefore taking into account the results of above mentioned physical experiments the Fick model was used for describing processes of moisture sorption in aramide composite and its components

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \sum_{i,j=1}^3 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(D_{ij} \frac{\partial C}{\partial x_j} \right), \tag{1}$$

where $i = 1$ — direction of reinforcement, D_{ij} — components of the coefficient tensor (DCT), C — moisture concentration. For a sample measuring $r_1 \times r_2 \times r_3$, the moisture content $W = \int_V C(x, t) dv$ was determined in sorption experiments.

Fig. 4. Moisture sorption kinetic (a) by composite samples at temperatures 5 (▲), 45 (◆), 60 °C (●, ■ — explanations in text) and 80 % RH; isotherms of moisture sorption (b) by binder (1), composite (2), and MP (3), empirical approximation (—).

Fig. 5. Graphs of dependences of moistening rate vs. moisture content for binder samples $r_1 = 2$ (1) and 3 mm (2) for $T = 60^\circ\text{C}$ and 80 % RH.

A calculation-experimental method tested on composite, binder, and MP, has been proposed for accelerated determination of the sorption characteristics of anisotropic material. The essence of the method consists of a combination of brief sorption experiments on samples of a given shape with subsequent calculation of the characteristics of the material. The equilibrium moisture content is determined by an extrapolation method which is based on the fact that the rate of the sorption process described by the Fick model decreases uniformly, asymptotically approaching zero. The moisture content approaches equilibrium value, which can be found with the graph of the dependence $dW/dt - W$ shown for example on Fig. 5.

Two independent components D_{11} and D_{22} of DCT can be found from results of two sorption experiments on samples of longitudinal and transverse (for example Fig. 4, ■ ●, respectively). The temperature dependence of the DCT components is satisfactory approximated with the Arrhenius equation

$$D_{ii} = D_{ii}^0 \exp(-U_{ii}^d/RT), \tag{2}$$

where $U_{ii}^d = 68$ kJ/mole and $D_{ii}^0 = 2.6 \cdot 10^7$ cm²/h for composite in fibre direction ($i = 1$); 52 and $2.3 \cdot 10^3$ transverse direction ($i = 2$); 60.6 and $1.05 \cdot 10^5$, respectively for binder.

The obtained results permit calculating estimations of the sorption characteristics of the composite on different structural levels: MP + binder — unidirectionally reinforced composite (monolayer) — multilayer composite. The equilibrium moisture content of the monolayer is determined with the rule of mixtures [5]

$$W_\infty^c = \mu W_\infty^r + (1 - \mu)W_\infty^b, \tag{3}$$

where the superscripts designate c — the composite, r — reinforcement MP, and b — binder, μ — reinforcement factor (with respect to volume).

The equations for calculating the diffusion coefficients of a composite in the direction of the reinforcement obtained from the condition of additivity of diffusion flows are reported in many studies (e.g., [6]), and for calculation of the transverse component of the DCT in [7, etc.]. The results of calculating the components of the DCT are given in Table 2, which shows that the precision of calculation of the longitudinal component of the tensor is satisfactory, and the value of the transverse component of the DCT can only be considered an estimation. The calculations of the transverse component with the different equations reported in the cited studies differ from each other by no more

Table 2. Diffusion characteristics of materials at 22 °C

Material	D_{11}	D_{22}
	$\times 10^{-6} \text{cm}^2/\text{h}$	
MP	40 ± 10	0.10 ± 0.05
Binder	1.9 ± 0.2	1.9 ± 0.2
Unidirectional composite		
Experimental	23 ± 2	1.4 ± 0.1
Calculated	25 ± 2	0.6 ± 0.1

than 20% and do not permit significantly improving the precision of the estimation. One of the key reasons for this is that in the general case, a jump in the concentration of moisture, whose value is a function of the materials of the phases and the current value of their moisture content, is observed on the interface of two adjacent sorbing phases. For this reason, the possibilities of a general analytical solution of the problem concerning the effective diffusion characteristics of a unidirectional composite are significantly limited.

Let us examine the question of migration of moisture on the i and $i + 1$ phase boundary, denoted as Q^i , in more detail. Two conditions should evidently be formulated for ensuring the uniqueness of the distribution function of the concentration of diffusant in the system studied on the phase boundary. It follows from the physical essence of these processes that one of them should be the condition of the equality of diffusion flows

$$(|j^i| = |j^{i+1}|)_{Q^i} \tag{4}$$

Another condition — equality of the chemical potentials of the diffusant ($\mu^i = \mu^{i+1}$) $_{Q^i}$. It was proposed in [8] that the chemical potential be represented as $\mu = RT \ln \varphi$, which results in the condition of equality of the moisture migration potential on the boundaries ($\varphi^i = \varphi^{i+1}$) $_{Q^i}$. Since the sorption isotherm is approximated by the empirical dependence $W_\infty^i = f^i(\varphi)$ in the general case, the condition for the concentration becomes

$$\{[f^i(W^i)]^{-1} = [f^{i+1}(W^{i+1})]^{-1}\}_{Q^i} \tag{5}$$

Fig. 6. Scheme of the plate.

Fig. 7. Moisture concentration profiles in a three-layer plate, matrix-fibre-matrix, at times 5 (1), 10 (2), 20 (3), 50 (4), 100 (5) and $200 \cdot 10^3$ hours (6).

Fig. 8. Calculated moisture sorption curves for composite (1), microplastics (2) and matrix (3) at 77% humidity.

where $[f^i(W^i)]^{-1}$ and $[f^{i+1}(W^{i+1})]^{-1}$ — reverse functions for $f^i(\varphi)$ and $f^{i+1}(\varphi)$ respectively. Analytical expressions for $f^i(\varphi)$ may differ for different phases.

The equations (1, 3-5) can be used for calculation of the moisture absorption characteristics for the composite on different structural levels. Moisture transport process in a thin parallel-plane multilayer plate under constant temperature and humid environmental conditions can be considered. We will study a model material which has no technological or other defects in the form of cracks unglued parts, or other perturbations of continuity. The kinetics of moisture absorption in a multilayer material also obey the relations in the Fick phenomenological model and are determined by two characteristics: the limiting moisture content and the components of the DCT. We will assume that the laminated composite is formed of different layers (Fig. 6). The algorithm and the program for moisture concentration field numerical calculation in the plate are worked out by Yu. V. Ivanov. The program was used for estimation of the moisture protection action of polymer covers. Another its application is moisture sorption in one-dimensional fibre composite modeling; it was proved to be good using an aramid composite example. For this material, moisture concentration distributions profiles for a three layer composite, matrix-fibre-matrix (Fig. 7), sorption curves and a sorption isotherm have been calculated. The last one has a good agreement with experimental data obtained previously. Stability of this result related to layer amount increase has been analyzed. For a two component composite considered a deviation in sorption character from the classic Fick law has been revealed though both components are in agreement with it (Fig. 8).

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